

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ELECTRODES

Parameters	Cu ²⁺ - sensitive electrode	Co ²⁺ - sensitive electrode
Nernstian response		
Slope (mV/p)	30	35
Working range (M)	1 × 10 ⁻¹ - 1 × 10 ⁻⁴	1 × 10 ⁻¹ - 5 × 10 ⁻⁵
Working pH range	3-8	2-8
Response time (s)	60	45
Life-time (week)	8	10

In order to exploit the electrode systems for determining the metal(II) ion directly in the presence of other cations, the selectivity coefficients were calculated by mixed solution method² for each electrode. The potentials in mixed solution against a constant background of foreign ions *viz.* Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mg²⁺, Co²⁺ (or Cu²⁺) at different concentrations were measured and the selectivity coefficients for the electrodes were found to be 1.00, 0.77, 0.15, 0.25, 0.25 for the Cu²⁺ sensitive electrode, and 0.29, 0.15, 0.10, 0.50 and 0.48, respectively for the Co²⁺ sensitive electrode.

Nitroso-R-salt forms³ 1:1 and 1:2 complex with Co²⁺ in aqueous solution in the acidic range of pH. In order to test the suitability of these electrodes, the stability constant of both the species was determined, using Co²⁺ ion sensitive electrode. The log K₁ (6.78) and log K₂ (5.48) values thus obtained agree with the literature values^{4,5}.

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Laser Raman Spectroscopic Investigation of SF₄ Molecule†

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THE sulphur tetrafluoride molecule has a geometrical configuration belonging to C_{2v} point group. The present investigation is aimed at obtaining the complete laser Raman vibrational

spectrum of the SF₄ molecule and to perform a normal coordinate treatment to obtain a set of reasonable molecular constants. Dodd *et al*¹ have reported the first vibrational spectrum of SF₄. Subsequently, several investigators^{2,3} have reported vibrational spectrum of SF₄ in solid and gas phase. In the present investigation, the laser Raman spectrum of SF₄, its assignment and the vibrational analysis are reported.

Frequency assignment : Spectroscopically pure SF₄ gas has been obtained from the Division of Applied Chemistry, Madras Institute of Technology. The laser Raman spectrum of SF₄ was recorded using 488 nm line of Ar⁺ for excitation in the region 100–2 000 cm⁻¹ on a Cary 82 grating spectrophotometer using 4W argon laser. The observed frequencies along with the assignment are presented in Table 1. The molecule gives rise to nine fundamental vibrations classified as 4A₁+A₂+2B₁+2B₂ and all the vibrations are Raman active.

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR PARAMETERS AND WAVE NUMBERS OF OBSERVED FUNDAMENTALS OF SF₄ MOLECULE

Species	Designation	Wave numbers cm ⁻¹	Description
A ₁	ν ₁	892vs(p)	ν _g -SF ₂ equatorial
	ν ₂	556vs(p)	ν _g -SF ₂ axial
	ν ₃	475m	δ _g cis-SF ₂ equatorial
	ν ₄	228w	δ _g cis-SF ₂ axial
A ₂	ν ₅	412vw	δ-SF ₂ twist
B ₁	ν ₆	867m	ν _{as} -SF ₂ axial
	ν ₇	532s	δ rock
B ₂	ν ₈	734vw	ν _{as} -SF ₂ equatorial
	ν ₉	351vw	δ wag

Structural parameters : D = 1.646 Å, d = 1.545 Å, R = 0.54 Å, α = 101°33', β = 86°32', γ = 129°15', η = 93°28'.

vs(p) = very strong (polarised), s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, vw = very weak.

The bands at 892 and 556 cm⁻¹ are strongly polarised and hence they belong to A₁ species. They are assigned to ν₁-SF₂ symmetrical and ν₂-SF₂ axial vibrations. The band set 867 and 734 cm⁻¹ are assigned to asymmetric S-F₂ axial stretching vibration (ν₆) and asymmetric SF₂ equatorial stretching (ν₈), respectively. These observations clearly agree with the available infrared data for this molecule. The bands at 475 and 228 cm⁻¹ appear to be closely polarised and hence they are assigned to A₁ type vibration, *i.e.* 475 cm⁻¹ is assigned to δ *cis*-SF₂ equatorial while 228 cm⁻¹ is assigned to δ *cis*-SF₂ axial. The band at 532 cm⁻¹ is depolarised and it is assigned to δ-rock ν₇. The band at 351 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν₉(B₂) from the previous data, on this molecule. The remaining fundamental SF₂ twisting mode is possible only in Raman spectrum and this frequency is assigned to 412 cm⁻¹. The present study agrees very well with the values reported in the literature for this molecule, especially with infrared spectrum

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Normal coordinate analysis: The assigned frequencies for these fundamentals and the structural parameters used in the present investigation are presented in Table 1. A normal coordinate analysis⁴⁻⁶ has been carried out and a set of molecular constants have been reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—KINETIC CONSTANTS (10^{-36} kg), VALENCE FORCE CONSTANTS (10^2 N m⁻¹) AND MEAN SQUARE AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION (10^{-3} Å²) OF SF₄ MOLECULE AT 298.16 K

	Kinetic constants <i>k</i>	Force constants <i>f</i>	Mean square amplitudes <i>σ</i>
<i>d</i>	4.112 83	5.582 32	2.546 45
<i>dd</i>	1.775 37	1.845 62	0.351 88
<i>D</i>	2.544 86	3.175 99	1.670 99
<i>DD</i>	0.649 19	-1.129 41	-0.633 44
<i>Dd</i>	0.119 97	0.151 34	0.077 10
<i>Dα</i>	-0.203 62	-0.163 00	0.015 23
<i>Dβ</i>	0.112 97	0.020 85	-0.031 45
<i>dα</i>	1.941 64	-1.554 49	0.621 14
<i>dβ</i>	1.196 09	0.220 79	-0.237 90
<i>α</i>	2.426 15	1.942 25	1.389 03
<i>αβ</i>	-1.002 05	-0.184 82	0.240 53
<i>β</i>	1.642 89	0.682 99	1.425 08
<i>ββ</i>	0.500 88	-0.034 27	0.119 31

Non-bonded mean amplitudes at 298.16 K (10^{-3} Å):
($F_1 - F_2$) = 8.061 82; ($F_3 - F_4$) = 6.697 83.

From Table 2, it is observed that the bond angle interaction kinetic constants $k_{Dα}$ and $k_{αα}$ and the angle-angle interaction constant $k_{αβ}$ are negative as expected. It is interesting to note that the corresponding force constants are also negative. The sign of force constant is a measure of localisation or delocalisation in a molecule⁷. Further, it is seen that $f_α$ is higher than f_D which suggests that the S-F_α bond is stronger than S-F₁ bond. The force constants evaluated are in the expected range.

The vibrational mean square amplitudes corresponding to the bonded lengths and the mean amplitudes corresponding to non-bonded lengths are evaluated in the present study and the values obtained in the expected range confirms the correctness of the assignment. The vibrational mean amplitude values are useful in the interpretation of electron diffraction data.

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Mode of Solidification and Flexural Strength of Naphthalene-Benzil System

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THE directional solidification is an important method for strengthening behaviour of eutectic alloys. The structural morphology and mechanical behaviour of directionally grown non-faceted-non-faceted binary eutectics were recently investigated^{1,2}. Significant work has been done on the morphological studies of directionally grown faceted-faceted samples³. Some investigations have been carried out on solidification and strength properties of faceted-non-faceted and non-faceted-non-faceted systems^{4,5}.

Investigations on flexural strengths of unidirectionally and randomly grown samples of naphthalene, benzil and their eutectic are presented in this paper. The results are interpreted on the basis of morphologies of these systems.

Experimental

Naphthalene (L.R., Reidel) was purified by slow sublimation followed by repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate and benzil (L.R., Loba) was purified by repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate. Eutectic (with eutectic temperature 51°) was prepared by accurately weighing the two components in the eutectic ratio (42 mole% of benzil)⁶. The unidirectional growth of naphthalene, benzil and their eutectic were carried out by the method described earlier⁷.

The single point loading method was used for the determination of flexural strength. The apparatus consisted of two knife edges (5.2 cm apart) and an arrangement for applying the load at the centre. The flexural strength has been calculated by the equation,

$$\sigma_f = \frac{8PL}{\pi d^3}$$

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